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THE INTEGRATION OF THE RENEWING UZBEKISTAN INTO THE WORLD
COMMUNITY AND GLOBAL ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

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ANNOTATION

In this article, it is revealed that many of the issues that plague mankind are directly or indirectly related to environmental problems, and their solution is taking place with the participation of human mind, thinking, intelligence, intellectual potential and, most importantly, values formed over the centuries. The authors have scientifically substantiated the fact that the measures taken in our republic to solve global ecological problems are actually a necessary factor for the healthy growth of a person. The article also examines issues of ensuring national and international security - guaranteeing the protection of human rights, integration of Uzbekistan into the world community in the field of human rights and freedoms, and global environmental problems.

Key words: nature, anthropogenic, New Uzbekistan, globalization, environmental policy, global problems, global environmental crises, environmental law, human rights, nature protection, natural resources.

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ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОННИНГ ЖАҲОН ҲАМЖАМИЯТИГА
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯЛАШУВИ ҲАМДА ГЛОБАЛ ЭКОЛОГИК МУАММОЛАР

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада инсониятни қийнаётган кўпгина масалалар экологик муаммолар билан бевосита ёки билвосита боғлиқ эканлиги, уларнинг ечими инсон онги, тафаккури, ақл-идроки, интеллектуал салоҳияти ва энг асосийси асрлар давомида шакланган кадриятлари иштирокида содир бўлаётганлиги очиб берилган. Муаллифлар, глобал экология муаммоларини ҳал этиш борасида республикамизда амалга оширилаётган тадбирлар аслида инсоннинг соғ-саломат яшаши учун зарур омил эканлигини илмий асослашган. Худди шунингдек, мақолада миллий ва халқаро хавфсизликни таъминлаш – инсон ҳуқуқларини ҳимоя қилиш кафолати, Ўзбекистоннинг инсон ҳуқуқлари ва эркинликлари соҳасида жаҳон ҳамжамиятига интеграциялашуви ҳамда глобал экологик муаммолар масалалари тадқиқ этилган.

Калит сўзлар: табиат, антропоген, Янги Ўзбекистон, глобаллашув, экологик сиёсат, глобал муаммолар, глобал экологик инқирозлар, экологик ҳуқуқ, инсон ҳуқуқлари, табиатни муҳофаза қилиш, табиий ресурслар.

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ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА В МИРОВОЕ СООБЩЕСТВО И ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье раскрывается, многие проблемы, беспокоящие человечество, прямо или косвенно связанные с экологическими проблемами, а их решение происходит при участии человеческого разума, мышления, интеллектуального потенциала и вековыми ценностями. Авторы научно обосновали тот факт, что принимаемые в нашей республике меры по решению глобальных экологических проблем на самом деле являются необходимым фактором здорового роста человека. Также в статье рассматриваются вопросы обеспечения национальной и международной безопасности – гарантии защиты прав человека, интеграции Узбекистана в мировое сообщество в области прав и свобод человека и глобальных экологических проблем.

Ключевые слова: природа, антропогенный, Новый Узбекистан, глобализация, экологическая политика, глобальные проблемы, глобальные экологические кризисы, экологическое право, права человека, охрана природы, природные ресурсы.

INTRODUCTION. Globalization processes taking place in the world today have an impact on the national democratic development, socio-demographic situation, immigration, economic, political and cultural life in the modernizing Uzbekistan. The fact that the new Uzbekistan is striving to take a place in the world community and develop through integration makes globalization a common reality in our national life.

In the process of establishing socio-ecological relations based on the principles of democracy and market economy in Uzbekistan, a new civilized system of environmental control institutions is being created, and its integration on a planetary scale is increasing. Deep scientific analysis of its national characteristics and laws of development is one of the most urgent problems.

Today, the criteria defining the ecological landscape of the world and mutuality of transformation processes determine the content and nature of global problems. Humanity lives in the vortex of global problems. "Today, we are living in a historical stage of human development, where sharp turns are taking place, so to speak.

The deepening reforms in our country, including modernization and democratization processes, require new ecological thinking, worldview, faith, ideology and high-quality management culture. This determines the relevance of deep scientific analysis of these processes.

In recent years, there have been drastic geopolitical changes on the earth, and the system of security and stability at the international level is falling apart. The increasingly intense globalization process not only expands the capabilities of humanity, but also leads to the aggravation of conflicts and the growing gap between developed and underdeveloped countries. As a result of this, various actions are being carried out, which are transnational in nature and scope, which undermine peace and stability" [1. 33], - says the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

The process of globalization, as in all spheres, in the ecological sphere, leads to different interpretations of the role and importance of the phenomenon of ecological worldview in the value system settled in the minds of people, their groups, social communities, and members of society as a whole. After all, issues related to the protection of nature, rational use of its resources, and the protection of human rights in the field of ecology are urgent problems.

Human existence, realization of political, economic and cultural rights depends on environment, nature and ecology. Man satisfies his needs through nature, he creates necessary tools, wealth and comforts from the blessings he received in the process of mastering nature. However, these appropriation processes have also created ecological problems of global importance, and now human life itself, its right to live, is in great anger. It is impossible to talk about human rights and freedoms without solving ecological problems, identifying the most difficult points and directions in this regard, and taking immediate measures. Without creating the necessary social and natural environment, without making it healthy, all thoughts about the right to life of a person will remain a pure subjectivism.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY. In world science, the research of the causes of environmental problems that threaten the future of humanity, the laws of development, driving motives, forms of manifestation, and modern philosophical issues of its elimination is gaining relevance. This requires studying the philosophical and methodological foundations of national values, the epistemological possibilities of modern scientific knowledge, and the characteristics of social existence based on the paradigms of modern science in the formation of the ecological worldview of a person. During the deepening of the process of liberalization and democratization of social, economic, political, environmental and other relations, the integration of the modernizing Uzbekistan into the world community and the management of society in general, prevention of global environmental problems, in particular, the institutional system of environmental control and its functional directions Uzbekistan It is detailed in the work of the President of the Republic Shavkat Mirziyoyev "New Uzbekistan - development strategy" [2].

At present, the globalization process and its related problems, the protection of human rights in the process of globalization are the focus of the world's leading scientists and specialists in various fields [4]. According to the American scientist T. Levitt, "globalization is the process of manufacturing goods and selling them in a way that unites the common activities of transnational corporations" [5. 13], this opinion was supported by Uzbek scientist B. Umarov [6. 8]. A. Pechchei "The global system of nature - man - society - technology is a total system" [7. 40] - and justifies the fact that global crises have arisen on earth due to scientific and technical discoveries and human greed.

The analysis of scientific sources shows that the study of the features of prevention of global environmental problems remains the main problem. Some aspects of the legal basis of prevention of global environmental problems were studied in scientific research works of Kalonov B.Kh., Kholmo'minov J., Mirzaev T.R., Roziev R., Najimov M., Ikramov R.A., B.M.Kandov, N.B.Shoimov [4].

The economic mechanisms of prevention of global environmental problems are reflected in candidate and doctoral theses of S.Samayilov, Sh.Karimov, N.Ikromova, S.K.Makhmudov, A.T.Umarov, A.Abdullaev.

Studying the philosophical aspects of environmental control in our republic is covered in scientific research works of scientists E. Khoshimova, Yu. Shodimetov, S. Mamashokirov, E. Usmonov, D. Rasilov, T. Quyliev, A. K. Berdimuradova, S. Sanginov, Sh. L. Makhmudova, V. O. Levinskaya, and U.Saidova.

Undoubtedly, the works, concepts and approaches of the above scholars are important for future researchers, but they did not directly research the problem of ensuring human rights in the context of globalization. In general, the above-mentioned researchers did not set themselves the goal of examining Uzbekistan's integration into the world community in the field of human rights and freedoms and global environmental problems as an object of socio-philosophical analysis.

The comments, theoretical conclusions presented in the article contribute to the scientific-methodological, socio-philosophical analysis of the institutional system of global ecological problems and the functional connections between them.

RESULTS. The concept of "human nature" is sometimes used in relation to a person. In this place, in fact, the signs and qualities that are naturally reflected in a person are meant. The concept and phrase "human nature" has been around since the time of Plato, but the relationship of man to nature has changed over the next four centuries. Man was viewed as a social person who mastered nature and even obeyed it. It is not the fact that a person belongs to nature that is appreciated, but what benefits, benefits, and wealth he receives, as a result, in the words of E. Fromm, "a person forgets that he is a person" [8. 154]. In this place, the philosopher refers to the impact of scientific and technical development on human nature, character, and activity. Therefore, he concludes that understanding human nature is more important today than ever [8. 154]. In this way, ecological ethics, that is, the measurement and assessment of a person's attitude to the environment and nature from the point of view of moral norms, appeared. Even Eugene Hargrow published articles in a journal called "Ecological Ethics", in which he discussed the relationship between man and nature, issues of modern technology, genetic engineering, organ transplantation, mass media and global marketing, from Aristotle to John Rawls. They "led to the understanding of ecological ethics as a form of practical philosophy" [9. 308-310]. The most important thing is that the ecological ethics that have arisen in the West, the Western way of life, the worship of scientific and technical achievements, the glorification of the individual as a god, the depiction of the power ruling over nature ("Sverchchelovek" by Fr. Nietzsche) have dangerous consequences. justifies the need to turn to the traditions of the East and study their views on the harmony of nature and man [9. 316-317]. In fact, the Jains who lived in the 8th-7th centuries BC, and later the Buddhists, believed that not to kill people, not to harm the surroundings, even trees and stones have souls. In their eyes, not only man, the whole existence is full of living beings, even the air consists of such invisible creatures (microbes, in modern terms). They should not be harmed or killed, that is why Jains encouraged people to walk with gauze around their mouths and wipe their feet [10. 277]. Similar thoughts and views are also found in "Avesta". The idea of the harmonious harmony of man with nature in general, the unity, commonality, integrity and equal value of the life of all living creatures has prompted the West to reconsider the attitude of man to civilization, especially to nature and ecology. From Arthur Schopenhauer's radical quietism to Albert Schweitzer's principle of "respect for life" led to the expansion of the scope of ethics, that is, the application of ethics to all living beings [11. 320-321], it was actually humanity's attempt to solve global environmental crises.

Natural planetary circulation processes that ensure the continuity and permanence of life take place on Earth. That is why Doctor of Philosophy, Professor E.S. KHoshimova, "Continuity, permanence of life exists in the form of biotic cycle. It is only because of this process that the continuity of life is preserved, in which one life process is connected with another. The interaction of all the components that make up the biosphere is reflected in the biotic cycle" [12. 15]. For example, "the process of matter circulation takes place on the basis of the principle of circulation and recirculation. One of the main characteristics of life on a global scale is the constant cycle of nitrogen

and phosphorus in nature. The influence of sunlight determines the biospheric thermal regime and the corresponding global circulation of the atmosphere and hydrosphere. In nature, due to the circulation of matter and energy, the components of the biosphere are interconnected and interact, and the ability of nature to resist, stabilize and restore itself is maintained. In the process of self-restoration, the relative balance of all living beings on earth is ensured and normal biophysical conditions are created" [12. 16]. Violation of this biotic cycle, the process of self-restoration and the relative balance of living beings has a negative impact on ecology, resulting in ecological crises.

A person can live in a certain natural environment. In order for him to fully live and function, his body temperature should not be higher than 420 and not lower than 250 [12. 18]. In the same way, the high air temperature should not exceed +600 and should not fall below -400. Experts say that if production and development continue in this way, the air temperature will almost double in two to two and a half centuries, and not only humans, but even microbes will not be able to live on earth [6. 4], they show that. At the same time, they promote the concept of developing an environmental policy on a global scale to rationally manage the situation. For example, according to the philosopher Usmanov E.M., in order to form an environmental policy in Central Asia it's necessary to : 1) collect statistical sources about the environmental situation in the region, create information, objective information bank; 2) arising from our people's ecological traditions and awareness of environmental protection; 3) development of alternative projects to increase the effectiveness of cooperation in the field of ecology; 4) it is necessary to be freed from the modeling of environmental policy in terms of narrow national interests [13. 28]. Unfortunately, the author does not mention that solving global environmental crises is primarily related to environmental law, and only this law can ensure interstate environmental integration. We believe that global environmental crises can only be resolved through global environmental law. Since Uzbekistan is building a democratic legal state, it is necessary to legally regulate people's relations with the environment, nature, and the use of nature in the production process. It is at this point that environmental law is combined with human rights and freedoms, environmental law is not only the protection of nature, but also the right of people to use nature's blessings and master nature.

In accordance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, environmental rights arise in the process of people's relations with nature, which are carried out within the framework of norms and procedures established by the state. In this place, the relationship of people to nature, natural resources, and the features of their use come to the fore. Therefore, nature and natural resources are not the private property of people, if they want to use these resources, they enter into certain legal relations with the owner of these resources.

In accordance with Article 214 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, land, underground resources, water, air space, flora and fauna are state-public property. However, this cannot prevent the realization of economic rights and freedoms of a person. In the same place, problems of state property and private property arise.

It is known that ecological and economic characteristics, i.e. human appropriation of nature, are considered as interrelated realities in property rights. Nature, land is at one time a real estate, and at another time a component of the natural environment that surrounds us. In this way, ecological and natural signs are simultaneously combined in nature, which requires a special approach to the object, natural resources from a legal point of view. Although they are a component of the environment, according to their objective qualities, they cannot be the object of appropriation or transformation into property, natural resources are left "unmaterialized". For example, atmospheric air, climatic reserves and similar natural phenomena cannot be turned into property. Some of them, for example, atmospheric air, can be used in order to determine the external borders of the state, the area where its jurisdiction (right to judge) is exercised. That is why in Article 19 of the Law "On Ownership in the Republic of Uzbekistan" the object of property rights is not directly atmospheric air, but an air basin" [14. 56]. Therefore, not all natural resources and reserves are private property.

DISCUSSION. The main cause of environmental problems is man, putting his own needs first. The concept of "anthropogenically changed environment" is used in scientific and theoretical literature. "Anthropogenic (Greek anthropos - person) changed environment is a natural environment

that has been fundamentally changed in a certain region or territory during the economic activity of people" [14. 196] is. The emergence of such an environment is related to the growth of production, desire to increase private property, interest in scientific and technical discoveries, wealth, and the boom in the use of property. As a result, not only acquiring wealth by exploiting natural resources, but also polluting the environment has become a global phenomenon. Today, almost all scientists who have studied global environmental problems note that environmental pollution is a result of those factors which have a negative impact on human health and gene pool. For example, natural areas, where atmospheric air has anthropogenically changed, is 10-15 times more polluted than other less affected natural environments. In industrial areas, the increase of toxic carbon dioxide (SO) in the air is mainly caused by metallurgy (30-40%) and chemical industry (15-20%), transport (10-15%), and in cities carbon dioxide is mainly caused by transport (60-80%), heavy industry (15-20%), chemical industry (5-10%). In agrarian tegras, the morphological (visible external) appearance of soils has changed radically up to a depth of 1-1.5 meters and formed a new type. In them, soil pollution occurs due to pesticides, herbicides, nitrogen, phosphorus, various salts, in cities - household waste, industrial waste in industrial plants. The amount of radioactive elements in the water, soil and atmospheric air around nuclear power plants belonging to the category of industrial plants is several tens times higher than in cities, but the amount of carbon dioxide around the power plant is equal to that of agricultural plants, and several dozen times more than in cities will be less [14. 270]. Therefore, Uzbek environmental scientists believe that it is necessary to increase the surface area per person from 5-10 m² to 25-30 m², depending on the size of the cities, the level of pollution, and climatic conditions [14. 271]. This is the main requirement for creating a healthy social and natural environment with clean air.

According to the information provided by the UN, various corporations and private property owners are producing about one million consumer goods on Earth that were not found in nature before. 100,000 of them consist of artificial compounds, and 15,000 are toxic, dangerous for human health and the environment [15. 214]. In recent years, it has been observed that most of the goods and products released to the consumer market in Uzbekistan do not meet the requirements of world standards. For example, half of the fruits and vegetables sold in the markets of the capital do not meet sanitary and hygienic requirements, and almost a third of them are contrary to the rules of consumption and sale. 12-15% of produced meat, fat, cheese products, 20-22% of sweets are not at the level of requirements [16]. As a result, respiratory, endocrine, cardiovascular, liver diseases, anemia, birth of weak children, cancer, gynecology, heart disease, bone fragility have increased 2-3 times in the cities. In rural areas, cases of anemia, tuberculosis, and chronic poisoning are observed in children under the age of 14 [17. 48-49]. In general, the production of raw materials, food, and beverages from artificial substances has become one of the global problems. Currently, about 6 million synthetic chemicals are used in the world. 200,000 new synthetic substances are added to their ranks every year. Unfortunately, the effects of most of these substances on living organisms and human health have not been determined [12. 53].

During the years of independence, extensive work was carried out in our Republic on the rational use of nature, the health of the environment, social and natural environment, special study centers of the Aral Sea and demography, migration problems, non-governmental organizations were established, environmental rights. More than 40 laws were adopted. In this place, the "EKOSAN" International Fund, the "Trust Fund" established on the basis of the United Nations Multilateral Partnership for Human Security for the Aral Sea region, the Central Asian countries' "Island Rescue" funds are examples. can be brought.

"EKOSAN" is a non-governmental organization dealing with issues of ecology and sanitation, involving international organizations in the research and practical solution of environmental problems. According to his concept, "ecology and sanology are viewed as the main indicators of the fields of politics, science, culture, and medicine" [18. 198]. From this perspective, it promotes the creation of an ecological-economic system in Central Asia that can be rationally managed from the point of view of the integrity of the biosphere, aimed at improving the health of the social and natural environment, and eliminating the crisis situations left over from the former USSR. At the same time,

there is a need to form a general environmental law system in the region, and to rely on international environmental law and UN documents on human rights and freedoms. "Currently, due to the Orol tragedy, the Orolkum desert has appeared on an area of more than 5.5 million hectares. 100 million tons of sand and salt are released into the air every year. This once again proves that the destruction of the island is a global problem" [3. 50]. Meeting growing economic and material needs without violating human rights and freedoms in accordance with the requirements of environmental law creates a number of problems. They put the following tasks on the agenda:

1. Ensure that human rights and freedoms, economic activity, and desires to fully enjoy material benefits are not violated in the rehabilitation of the social and natural environment. Health of the social and natural environment should not deny private property, creation of new production methods through entrepreneurship, opening of new enterprises, development of lands, creation of benefits. At the same time, the market economy, entrepreneurship and business should not lead to destruction of the ecological system, to engage in labor activities that harm human health.

2. People should socially monitor the compliance of production enterprises with sanitary-hygiene rules and norms established by international law. Experience shows that individuals and groups seeking to gain wealth at the expense of people's health can easily achieve their goals if the people do not always control which enterprise, firm, and economic entity produces what and what kind of quality products. Just as people have the right to buy and consume clean, pure and harmless products, they also have the right to monitor the activities of entities that produce these products.

3. Today, ecological problems have gained global importance. Inter-state, inter-regional economic integration is rapidly spreading the produced products, goods, blessings to the whole world. A tangerine grown in Iran or coffee harvested in Brazil appears in the markets of Uzbekistan in three to four days. However, compliance of these benefits with sanitary and hygienic standards is not always checked. Therefore, it is necessary to organize monitoring institutes to monitor and study compliance of finished products with international sanitary and hygienic standards. It is true that in Uzbekistan there are no cases of mass poisoning of the population, especially children, as in Russia, but the quality of most of the goods and gifts brought from abroad is not high.

4. In the recent past, "EKOSAN" put forward the idea of implementing "Clean water" and "Clean air" programs in Central Asia. In this regard, "EKOSAN" together with international organizations organized sanitary and educational events in the vicinity of the Aral Sea, and attended public meetings. In our opinion, similar events should be held again, they should be organized in the whole region and regions.

5. It is necessary to develop universal norms of nature protection, use of natural resources, to harmonize the norms of environmental law in the republics with each other and with international environmental law. It cannot be forgotten that environmental problems are of global importance. The most important thing is that these norms should be based on principles that do not interfere with the realization of human rights and freedom, do not interfere with the healthy and vigorous growth of a person, do not destroy the socio-natural environment, ecological balance, and "biotic cycle".

CONCLUSION. Today, ecology and environmental crises are a global problem that threatens the human right to live and work freely. No country on earth is exempt from this problem. It is necessary to develop universal norms of nature protection, use of natural resources, to harmonize the norms of environmental law in the republics with each other and with international environmental law. These standards are based on principles that do not interfere with the realization of human rights and freedoms, do not interfere with the healthy and vigorous growth of a person, do not disturb the socio-natural environment, ecological balance, and increase the effectiveness of the international environmental rights activities, depending on the use of optimal methods and tools with a differential approach to national and regional characteristics.

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